

CHROMATOGRAPHIC ESTIMATION OF SMALL AMOUNTS OF PHOSPHATES

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A chromatographic method of estimating phosphates in small quantities has been developed and used in the estimation of P_2O_5 in bone ash.

Briggs (*J. Biol. Chem.* 1922, 53, 13) has described a colorimetric method of estimating inorganic phosphates in urine by the blue colour produced in 30 minutes by the phosphomolybdate hydroquinone complex. This method did not give concordant results with the ends of samples of bone matter under ossification in normal and abnormal (dwarf) human foetus, since (i) in dilute solutions the blue colour of the complex was difficult to match with the standard quite sharply, and (ii) the reaction was not completed in 30 minutes, and in concentrated solutions the depth of the colour was produced much more rapidly. Hence, a chromatographic method of estimating P_2O_5 content of bone ash has been developed and adopted. Schwab and Dattler (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1937, 50, 691) have shown that anions can be separated into zones of chromatographic order and PO_4''' takes the first place among these anions. Preliminary experiments have shown that the alumina, buffered to pH 5.4, yields good chromatograms.

EXPERIMENTAL

Alumina of -90 + 120 mesh was prepared as previously (*this Journal*, 1949, 26, 415) and dried at 170° for 4 hours.

The column was formed in tubes of uniform bore of 3.4 mm. The tubes were drawn off to a tapering end and were plugged with cotton wool. The tubes were first filled with a buffer solution of pH 5.4 (made from 50 c.c. of potassium hydrogen phthalate + 5.5 c.c. $M/5$ NaOH and made up to 200 c.c.). The dry alumina of mesh -90 + 120 was added in small quantities at a time. This method was found to give a well packed column without any air bubbles being entrapped. The tubes so filled were placed in jars containing the buffer solution and left overnight before use. These columns were allowed to drain and used immediately for chromatograms.

Measured quantities of phosphate solutions were passed through the column. The adsorbed column was washed three or four times with distilled water and the nitroammonium molybdate solution was used as a developer. A fine yellow chromatogram with sharp edges was produced. As the developer descended, the yellow complex, composed of large sized molecules, rendered its passage rather difficult and slow. A gentle suction was helpful in such cases though the last step took a few hours. The chromatograms were regular and uniform and the results were reproducible.

Evaluation of the Constant (1/n) in the Adsorption Isotherm

It has been pointed out in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) that for each ion and the chromatographic tube the value of $1/n$ in Freundlich's isotherm has to be found out.

For different concentrations of the same ion, we have

$$(c_1/c_2)^{1/n} = h_2/h_1$$

where c_1 and c_2 are different concentrations of the ions and h_1 and h_2 are their respective chromatographic heights, produced by them. 0.2 c.c. and sometimes 0.4 c.c. of each of the two solutions of sodium phosphate (pure crystals analysed to $\text{Na}_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were passed through the columns in the separate tubes; the column was washed with water and developed with 0.2 to 0.4 c.c. of nitroammonium molybdate solution. The following table contains the data.

TABLE I

1. Solution 149.5 mg. of P_2O_5 /100 c.c.		2. Solution 294.5 mg. of P_2O_5 /100 c.c.	
Vol. (c.c.)	0.2	0.4	0.2
Length (mm.)	5.0	10	10.0

$$\text{Hence, } \left[\frac{149.5}{294.5} \right]^{-\frac{1}{n}} = \frac{10}{5}$$

$$\text{or } -1/n = 1.023$$

Estimation of P_2O_5 in the Samples of Bones.—The samples of bones were carefully ashed in a weighed platinum crucible and weighed. The ash was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and the solution made up to 100 c.c., 0.5 c.c. aliquots of which were chromatographed and the results obtained are recorded in Table II. Each experiment was repeated at least thrice; averages of values not differing by more than 1 mm. were taken. The value of $1/n (-1.023)$ was used to calculate the P_2O_5 content in each sample. Allowance had been made for the fact that the reference chromatogram was with 0.2 c.c. of solution, whereas here 0.5 c.c. was used.

Since 0.5 c.c. was used, the proportionate heights from table were taken as the height of chromatogram was proportional to the volume of the solution used at the same concentration.

The last column gives the data by the colorimetric method, under the best of conditions.

TABLE II

Sample No.	Height of chromatogram.	P_2O_5 in 100 c.c.	Ash.	% P_2O_5 in ash.	
				A.	B.
N_1	2.0 mm.	26.04 mg.	62.0 mg.	41.91	44.30
N_2	10.8	130.0	335.0	39.46	34.31
N_3	15.0	177.9	476.0	37.37	45.63
AN_1	8.5	103.5	516.0	20.06	24.18
AN_2	16.5	194.8	782.0	24.91	29.73
AN_3	2.0	26.04	70.0	37.20	—

A—Chromatographic method.

B—Colorimetric method (*loc. cit.*)